

Policy Brief (D3.4 Transformative strategies, and just governance and intersectionality)

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- 1 PU = Public
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Summary

Summary of Deliverable

Intersectionality and gender equality have become priorities in research and innovation since the EU's commitment to the European Research Area (ERA) Framework and the Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025. When the EU Biodiversity Strategy encountered ERA's inclusiveness agenda, it highlighted the need to understand how interlocking social asymmetries shape both biodiversity loss and the governance responses designed to address it.

Based on nine case studies across Europe — in sectors such as agriculture, urbanisation, forestry, and aquatic resources, this policy brief presents the main findings of Deliverable 3.4 of the BIOTraCes project, outlining how just biodiversity governance can be achieved in the European context. By exploring the connection between transformative strategies and just biodiversity governance, it offers recommendations that combine gender mainstreaming, diversity promotion, and effective governance for biodiversity regeneration. It brings together:

- key messages emerging from the analysis of interventions carried out by societal partners and through collaboration with research partners;
- a context analysis examining how gender equity and diversity concerns intersect with biodiversity governance;
- a set of recommendations for strengthening just and inclusive transformative strategies.

The methodological trajectory and analytical steps underpinning these findings are described in more detail in Section 8 of Deliverable 3.2.

To support targeted action, the brief provides tailored recommendations for three groups of policymakers:

1. EU-level sectoral and environmental policymakers,
2. R&I policymakers shaping Nature-based Solutions agendas, and
3. local governance bodies and technical staff involved in biodiversity regeneration.

By bridging gender equality, diversity, and biodiversity governance, this policy brief underscores that ecological transformation requires governance models that value plural knowledge, care, and the leadership of those most affected by environmental change.

Just Biodiversity Governance

Biodiversity and Transformative Change for Plural and Nature Positive Societies

How can transformative strategies promote just biodiversity governance?

Key messages

- **Biodiversity loss not only undermines ecological resilience but also exacerbates gender inequalities.** Women sustain vital connections between people and nature — from agriculture and water management to forest stewardship — yet these interdependencies are increasingly threatened. Rural and low-income women are among the most vulnerable: they depend heavily on local ecosystems for food, water, and fuel, yet often lack secure land rights, access to finance, or a voice in governance. Recognising women as key actors in biodiversity protection is therefore essential to achieving just and inclusive governance.
- Systemic barriers – such as **limited access to land, finance, training, and policymaking platforms**, in addition to persistent stereotypes – reduce women's visibility and influence in biodiversity governance.
- When biodiversity-rich forests are degraded, women's opportunities to generate livelihoods and sustain family wellbeing shrink disproportionately. When rivers are polluted, forests cleared, or land privatised, **women are often left with fewer alternatives to secure livelihoods and household wellbeing**, amplifying their exposure to biodiversity loss. Indigenous and rural women are even more affected by this scenario.
- In agriculture, women face a **double vulnerability**: they are less likely to own land or control productive resources, and more likely to depend on small-scale, biodiversity-rich farming systems that are directly threatened by intensification and land degradation.
- Women should be recognised by policymakers not only as a vulnerable group but as **agents of change**. It means fostering policies at local, national and European level that value women's contributions in agriculture, forestry, water management, urbanisation and community-led innovation.
- **Women are not a homogeneous group.** Social markers such as race, ethnicity, class, age, sexual identity, and nationality intersect to deepen asymmetries in both access to resources and exposure to risks. Policies must therefore acknowledge and address these intersecting inequalities to ensure fair and effective outcomes.
- **Persistent underrepresentation in governance.** Vulnerable groups (women, youth, elderly people, children) and marginalised populations (migrants, Roma, racialised communities, transgender people) remain underrepresented in decision-making — including in biodiversity governance. Local authorities and organisations usually neglect the extent to which regeneration decision-making processes often exclude women and marginalised groups.
- R&I organisations' capacity to collect robust and reliable equality data related to biodiversity regeneration processes depends on an ongoing effort to raise awareness among institutions on the way **climate change is gendered** and the relevance of gender-responsive strategies. **Transformative change in biodiversity governance depends on four key dimensions**: the validation of plural perspectives, including those of underrepresented groups (**pluralising**); the embedding of regenerative strategies into everyday social, economic, and political life (**embedding**); the integration of transformation into political decision-making (**politicising**); and sustained attention to the communities' agency and resilience (**empowering**). Together, these principles underpin BIOTraCes' commitment to just and inclusive governance.

Context Analysis

European biodiversity governance has advanced through strategies such as the **EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030** and the **Nature Restoration Regulation**. These frameworks emphasise restoration, sustainable land use, and ecosystem resilience. However, they remain largely gender-blind: women's differentiated roles, knowledge, and vulnerabilities are rarely considered in their design or monitoring. Governance processes continue to be dominated by some stakeholders – large landowners, industrial actors, or state authorities – while communities, smallholders, women, and minorities often face only symbolic inclusion (European Commission, 2020; European Environment Agency, 2020; IUCN, 2021).

The absence of gender perspective is not a minor omission, but a structural weakness that undermines policy legitimacy. By failing to integrate gender perspectives, governance risks reinforcing existing inequalities in access to resources, decision-making power, and ecological benefits.

Intersectionality and gender equality have become priorities in research and innovation since the European Union committed itself to the European Research Area (ERA) Framework and the Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025. As a result of the increasing dialogue between EU Biodiversity Strategy and ERA Research & Innovation Framework, policy making was demanded to pay closer attention to interlocking asymmetries and their effects in biodiversity loss. It is grounded on the evidence that gender inequalities intersect with race, disability, socioeconomic background, or sexual orientation (European Commission & Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2025). As such, it is now known that disadvantaged women – rural, migrant, indigenous – have faced compounded disadvantages, making it essential to design adaptation and mitigation strategies that account for multiple, overlapping inequalities.

Gender inequalities in environmental issues have material effects. Across high-impact sectors, persistent gaps remain evident and require urgent attention.

Although women are 31.6% of farm operators, the share of farms managed by women varies sharply – reaching around 45% in Latvia and Lithuania but falling below 10% in Germany, Denmark, and the Netherlands. In organic farming, the share is even lower (26.9%), despite evidence that women-led farms adopt more agro-environmental and climate measures (Eurostat, 2020). Women in forestry, in turn, account for just 20% of the workforce in Europe, often concentrated in seasonal or informal roles with less income security and representation (UNECE/FAO, 2023). With regard to water governance, women remain underrepresented in ministries, councils, and community bodies responsible for water and land management, even though they are primary users of these resources for food, water, and care work (IUCN, 2021; CBD Secretariat, 2009).

These impacts are not gender neutral. Women, especially those in rural and low-income communities, are among the most vulnerable: they depend heavily on ecosystems for food, water, and fuel, yet often lack secure land rights, access to finance, or a voice in governance. As a result, biodiversity loss not only undermines ecological resilience but also exacerbates gender inequalities, making women disproportionately affected by its consequences.

Linking gender to biodiversity governance is therefore essential. Without integrating women's contributions and intersectional perspectives, governance risks reproducing inequalities and undermining its own ecological objectives. Conversely, just and effective governance can emerge when policies explicitly recognise how biodiversity and gender are interdependent – ensuring that strategies for ecological resilience also advance social equity.

Based on nine case studies across Europe, in sectors such as agriculture, urbanisation, forestry, and aquatic resources, **BIOTraCes – Biodiversity and Transformative Change for Plural and Nature-Positive Societies** has not only shed light on the institutional lock-ins that hinder effective action against biodiversity loss, but also examined what effective and just biodiversity governance can look like, giving attention to both gender equity and the participation of vulnerable and disadvantaged groups in governance processes.

This policy brief thus explores the connection between transformative strategies and just biodiversity governance, providing policymakers with recommendations that combine gender mainstreaming, diversity promotion, and governance for biodiversity regeneration.

Why Gender Matters for Biodiversity Governance

- **Gender-blind governance is a structural weakness:** EU biodiversity policies such as (Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and, Nature Restoration Law, NBS) remain largely blind to women's roles and vulnerabilities, undermining their legitimacy (European Commission, 2020; EEA, 2020; IUCN, 2021).
- **Women are underrepresented across sectors:** They account for **31.6% of farm operators** (Eurostat, 2020), only **20% of the forestry workforce** (UNECE/FAO, 2023), and are largely absent from water and land governance bodies (IUCN, 2021; CBD Secretariat, 2009).
- **Biodiversity loss exacerbates inequality:** More than **80% of EU habitats and species are in poor or inadequate conservation status** (EEA, 2020), hitting rural and low-income women hardest as they depend more directly on ecosystems for food, water, and livelihoods.
- **Intersectionality compounds vulnerabilities:** Rural, migrant, indigenous, and minority women often face overlapping disadvantages, making them disproportionately affected by biodiversity decline (EC, 2025; UN Women, 2024).
- **Inclusive governance strengthens resilience:** Recognising women's ecological knowledge (food, seed keeping, care, education) and ensuring meaningful participation leads to more **effective, just, and sustainable biodiversity outcomes** (CBD Secretariat, 2009; UNESCO, 2021).

Main Findings on Just Governance

The research evinced the following state of play:

Barriers to Transformative Governance

- **Persistent underrepresentation of marginalised groups in biodiversity governance.** Decision-making processes in biodiversity governance remain dominated by established actors, with minority women, migrant families, Roma, and racialised communities largely absent or only sporadically involved. Where inclusion mechanisms exist, participation often remains symbolic rather than influential, reflecting broader asymmetries in power and recognition.
- **Contradictions between policy commitments and implementation practices.** Although European and national frameworks increasingly endorse biodiversity-oriented approaches, their translation into local practice remains fragmented and constrained by the procedural conditions set by high-impact sectors' regulations. This reveals a structural mismatch between high-level policy commitments and the operational flexibility required for effective territorial implementation. As a result, local initiatives aligned with EU priorities towards biodiversity frequently face conflicting regulations and rigid administrative requirements.
- **Bureaucratic obstacles and entrenched governance routines.** Across the contexts analysed, long-standing administrative practices and rigid governance procedures continue to compromise the integration and scaling of local innovations. Although some territories have begun to experiment with more adaptive and collaborative approaches, including co-governance models, public administration largely remains opaque and top-down. These barriers to innovation are not only technical or financial but deeply embedded in governance cultures that prioritise compliance and control over experimentation and collaboration.
- **Local sensitiveness and the need for context-sensitive approaches.** While most initiatives showed alignment with environmental goals, tensions emerged when ecological transitions conflicted with existing economic interests. Resistance was also evident around social concepts such as gender and minorities, often seen as externally imposed or not fully resonant with local realities. These reactions underscore the importance of engaging with how such concepts are understood in specific settings and of addressing the underlying tensions that make them contentious — rather than simply adapting the language to avoid discomfort.

- **Disconnection between biodiversity goals and social justice concerns.** Environmental objectives are frequently pursued without acknowledging the social dimensions of biodiversity loss — particularly how inequality, gender relations, and power asymmetries shape both its causes and its impacts. As a result, regeneration efforts risk reproducing existing exclusions rather than challenging social, political, and cultural lock-ins that continue to block transformative change.
- **Gendered and intersectional impacts of environmental change remain unaddressed.** Environmental initiatives seldom account for the differentiated impacts of biodiversity loss and climate risks across genders. The gendered dimensions of vulnerability — particularly affecting rural and marginalised women — remain underreported and largely absent from biodiversity governance. The persistent lack of gender-sensitive data and indicators prevents a proper evaluation of how regenerative strategies align with equity and justice goals, resulting in a continued gap with the standards promoted under the ERA R&I framework.
- **Underrecognition of women’s contributions to regeneration.** Despite growing evidence of women’s central role in shaping adaptation and mitigation responses, as well as in everyday ecological care, their contributions remain largely invisible within biodiversity governance. Women’s knowledge on food security and sovereignty, preservation of native seeds, and care work continues to be treated as informal or peripheral, rather than as a vital component of regenerative transitions. This persistent undervaluation limits both the inclusiveness and the transformative potential of biodiversity strategies.
- **Neglect of spatial justice and non-human agency.** Spatial justice remains a largely unaddressed aspect of biodiversity governance. The social dimension of how space and landscapes are shaped, accessed, and redistributed receives little attention within regenerative approaches. Territorial inequalities and unequal access to land and ecosystems persist. At the same time, biodiversity discourse continues to privilege a resource-based view of nature, overlooking the agency and rights of non-human entities. While native species and habitat restoration are frequently invoked, these efforts seldom engage with the broader ethical and relational dimensions of regeneration. Addressing environmental and spatial justice therefore requires recognising both human and more-than-human forms of interdependence and responsibility.
- **Neglect of traditional and tacit knowledge.** Across territories, diverse forms of experience-based knowledge — often held by small producers and local communities — remain undervalued compared to formal or technological solutions. These tacit forms of understanding, rooted in situated practice and long-term engagement with the land, have proven essential for both ecological awareness and social cohesion. Recognising and integrating such knowledge into regenerative governance frameworks is not only a matter of equity, but also a source of innovation and resilience.

- **Fragility of community-based initiatives.** Community-based initiatives have played a vital role in embedding biodiversity in everyday life, yet they remain structurally fragile. Their continuity depends largely on project-based funding and temporary support mechanisms, with limited integration into formal policy frameworks. While these initiatives have proven essential for local regeneration, their long-term sustainability requires stable institutional recognition, consistent resources, and stronger links to territorial governance.
- **Emerging Innovations and Promising Practices**
Concurrently, emerging innovations reveal tangible steps towards regenerative transition:
- **Attention towards pluralising, embedding, politicising, and empowering.** The findings evince concrete efforts across the cases to advance transformative change through pluralising, embedding, politicising, and empowering practices (the BIOTraCes PEPE principles). These efforts can be seen in attempts to broaden the range of actors and knowledges involved in decision-making, to root transformative initiatives within situated social and ecological realities, to expose and rework unequal relations of power in governance processes, and to strengthen communities’ collective capacity to influence change. Together, these orientations reveal how transformative innovations are being shaped through experimentation, negotiation, and the pursuit of more inclusive and context-sensitive forms of governance.
- **Creative and inclusive engagement approaches.** New participatory formats have succeeded in reaching actors usually distant from formal decision-making. Artistic, performative, and experiential activities have proven particularly effective in lowering social and cultural barriers to participation, creating spaces where different forms of expression and knowledge can coexist. These experiences demonstrate that inclusive engagement can enhance both legitimacy and creativity in local governance.

- **Co-governance models.** Emerging partnerships between public institutions and civil society actors have been experimented with more horizontal forms of governance. These models – based on shared agendas and mutual accountability – challenge the persistence of hierarchical routines and open room for collaborative problem-solving. Though still fragile, they signal a growing institutional willingness to redistribute responsibility and to value shared ownership of territorial strategies.
- **Recognition of multiple forms of knowledge and agency.** There is a growing awareness that scientific and technical expertise alone cannot sustain biodiversity regeneration. Local, experiential forms of knowledge – often transmitted through practice, care, and lived interaction with the land – are increasingly recognised as vital components of transition. By valuing these contributions, recent initiatives have fostered more inclusive and grounded understandings of regeneration, bridging analytical frameworks with community experience. Co-learning processes and situated experimentation have begun to reconfigure how knowledge circulates across research, policy, and practice, signalling a gradual shift toward more plural and dialogical approaches to governance.
- **Translocal collaboration.** Innovative connections emerged between community actors, researchers, and public institutions, as well as among territories facing similar challenges. These exchanges have enabled mutual learning and the adaptation of successful practices, fostering solidarity-based networks that transcend administrative and geographical boundaries. Such connections are beginning to shape a shared sense of purpose

across diverse contexts, reinforcing the idea that regeneration depends not only on local action but also on the circulation of knowledge and care across scales.

- **Networks of mutual learning.** Collaborative platforms connecting community actors, researchers, and institutions have shown potential to build shared understanding, foster peer learning across territories, and enable concerted action. Beyond knowledge transfer, they nurture trust and reciprocity, reinforcing a collective sense of purpose among actors navigating similar challenges. Although still emerging, such networks represent a promising foundation for collective learning and the long-term consolidation of regenerative practices.
- **Commitment to social cohesion and collective learning.** Strengthening community participation and social cohesion have emerged as key elements for advancing regenerative transitions. Initiatives that cultivate trust, dialogue, and mutual recognition are helping to rebuild the social fabric needed for long-term change. Beyond improving coordination, these efforts foster a shared sense of belonging and collective purpose, gradually shifting local imaginaries towards cooperation, care, and reciprocity. By embedding learning and collaboration within everyday community life, they contribute to making regeneration a socially grounded process rather than a purely technical goal.
- **Ecological literacy and intergenerational learning.** Educational and community-based initiatives have begun to foster ecological literacy and awareness across generations. By linking practical experience with collective reflection, these activities strengthen people's emotional and cultural connection to land, water, and biodiversity. They also help integrate ecological values into everyday practices, encouraging a sense of stewardship that extends beyond individual action. Through these learning processes, regeneration becomes not only an environmental goal but also a shared cultural project rooted in continuity, care, and transmission of knowledge.

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Specific Recommendations

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For Just Biodiversity Governance at National and European level

- Embed regenerative criteria into high-impact sectors' funding.** Incorporate biodiversity regeneration and conservation criteria into funding schemes for high-impact sectors, rewarding the adoption of regenerative practices such as soil improvement, reduction of livestock density impacts, wildlife management, and the use of nature-based solutions (NbS) in urban and rural settings.
- Encourage the creation of transition insurance policies at the Member State level.** Finance transition-insurance schemes to de-risk experimentation and support experimental techniques in areas threatened by climate change and biodiversity loss. Develop specific calls and credit facilities to cover the initial costs of transformative strategies by companies, cooperatives, and regenerative entrepreneurs at local, regional, and national levels. Transition insurance should create long-term support mechanisms that allow regenerative techniques to flourish and be widely disseminated.
- Promote regenerative funding to reduce economic and social vulnerabilities.** Create calls that support young people to remain in their territories by developing regenerative practices as viable economic activities. Develop funding schemes that recognise and reward rural women's participation in biodiversity governance, particularly in mitigation and adaptation strategies.
- Enhance the practical coordination between EU green policy instruments.** While the Green Deal, Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), and Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) share overarching goals, their implementation often follows parallel tracks. Greater operational alignment is needed to ensure that biodiversity and regeneration objectives are consistently integrated across all funding and policy frameworks.
- Adapt EU funding mechanisms to territorial realities.** Simplify procedures and introduce flexibility within EU and national funding schemes so that small-scale, community-led, and experimental initiatives can access and manage resources more easily. This includes revising eligibility criteria that currently privilege large-scale applicants.
- Foster multi-level governance and accountability.** Promote stronger collaboration between EU, national, and local authorities to ensure that biodiversity policies are context-sensitive and accountable to affected communities. Encourage participatory monitoring mechanisms that integrate local perspectives and knowledge in decision-making processes.
- Apply gender and representativeness indicators in nature-based solutions (NbS) projects.** Require biodiversity and NbS projects to apply gender and representativeness indicators, supported by qualitative and gender-sensitive monitoring frameworks, to evaluate participation and ensure that tailored, intersectional measures address the distinct impacts of biodiversity loss and climate change on rural, migrant, urban, Indigenous, and elderly women.
- Reinforce the European Research Area (ERA) through inclusive knowledge systems.** Strengthen the connection between research, policy, and local action by supporting participatory science, open data practices, and recognition of diverse forms of expertise in biodiversity governance. This approach should complement gender and equity objectives already embedded in the ERA R&I policy agenda.
- Foster mechanisms for self-evaluation and representativeness in governance.** The EU should encourage national, regional, and local organisations to evaluate how representativeness is ensured, not only to reduce biases in biodiversity strategies, but also to enable different perspectives to question and reshape decisions. Supporting mechanisms for dialogue and negotiation allows tensions and disagreements to be addressed constructively, turning them into opportunities for more democratic and grounded biodiversity governance.
- Create conditions to move beyond awareness-raising and capacity-building towards genuine empowerment.** Promote frameworks, actions, and plans that make member States and organisations to ensure communities and local actors hold real decision-making power. Secure long-term financial and institutional support for community-led initiatives, recognise everyday forms of community leadership engaged with biodiversity regeneration, and value care, reciprocity, and collective agency as foundations of transformative governance. Genuine empowerment requires transferring not only skills but also the means and legitimacy to act, ensuring that those most affected by ecological transitions can shape them directly.

For Inclusive Gender Equity in R&I in EU

- **Mainstream gender in biodiversity research.** Promote gendered innovations and expand ERA monitoring to systematically integrate gender considerations across discussions and projects on biodiversity, climate, and regenerative governance.
- **Promote training in intersectional approaches.** Provide capacity building for researchers working on nature-based solutions and biodiversity, including funding opportunities for those applying intersectional methodologies. Capturing the lived experiences of biodiversity loss is crucial for generating evidence-based research to inform gender-responsive strategies in biodiversity governance.
- **Strengthen gender equality and diversity data in governance.** Mainstream data on gender equality and diversity representation into EU and national biodiversity governance surveys, in order to provide a more accurate picture of how biodiversity loss is gendered and disproportionately affects marginalised populations.
- **Raise civil society awareness and foster local engagement.** Promote public awareness of the relevance of inclusive gender equity in innovation and actively engage local organisations and authorities, whose buy-in is essential to overcome resistance and integrate gender considerations into biodiversity agendas. Overcoming local resistance to change is essential for achieving the inclusive gender equity goals set by the European Commission.
- **Engage key stakeholders in high-impact sectors.** Agriculture, forestry, aquatic resources, and urbanisation actors should be mobilised to effectively incorporate biodiversity guidelines and embed inclusive gender equity into sectoral policies. Without this dual integration, regional, national, and EU-level policies risk undermining biodiversity regeneration efforts and perpetuating gender inequalities in environmental governance.

For Gender- and Diversity-Sensitive Approaches in Biodiversity Governance at Local and Regional level

- **Promote training of local actors.** Equip municipalities, forest councils, water committees, and NGOs with skills to identify gender-differentiated risks (e.g., access to credit, mobility issues, adaptation investments).
- **Strengthen co-governance.** Ensure that the voices of women, Roma, migrants, youth, and elderly people are integrated into governance bodies through co-designed and inclusive mechanisms.
- **Support inclusive entry points.** Promote small-scale, low-barrier strategies that reduce dependence on long-distance transportation of goods and stimulate regional economic networks. Recognise and validate forms of community resilience – such as community seed banks or women’s herder networks – as starting points for broader governance inclusion.
- **Recognise the heterogeneity of women.** Provide tailored, intersectional responses that address how rural, migrant, urban, Indigenous, and elderly women are differently affected by biodiversity loss and climate change.
- **Stimulate living labs for inclusivity.** Develop EU-supported living labs that co-create biodiversity solutions with local communities, ensuring governance processes feel locally grounded rather than externally imposed.
- **Support diverse local economy models.** Promote cooperatives, social and solidarity economy initiatives, and other collaborative models not only to stimulate regeneration but also to mitigate the economic impact of adaptation.
- **Mitigate local transition costs.** Address the initial costs of adopting regenerative practices, techniques, and technologies to make adaptation strategies viable. Create small funding lines for experimentation in multi-challenged territories (e.g., regions facing desertification, depopulation, and ageing populations).
- **Encourage innovative, inclusive community-based business models.** Integrate small and medium-sized entrepreneurs into local regenerative policies and strategies, with special focus on young people and women. Support diverse business models and local arrangements (cooperatives, community-based economies, partnerships between social economy entities, local authorities, small producers, and local development associations) focused on regeneration.

” Closing remarks

Much has already been achieved in promoting policies and strategies aimed at transformative change and biodiversity regeneration. However, to deliver more durable and scalable results — in terms of long-term change, community engagement, and the diffusion of transformative effects across territories — these efforts would benefit from stronger alignment across local, national, and European levels. Such alignment would help eliminate internal inconsistencies and enhance the overall effectiveness and visibility of actions.

Moreover, concerted action is needed between three key areas:

1. policy and governance frameworks promoting just and inclusive approaches at national and European levels;
2. strategies on transformative-related research and innovation that identify, validate, and emphasise the connections with gender equality;
3. local strategies ensuring gender equality and diversity in place-based regenerative actions and plans.

Closer synergy among these three dimensions would strengthen communication and coherence between the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and the ERA Framework — the latter being particularly attentive to how Europe addresses inclusive gender equality in research and innovation. Besides, **pluralising, embedding, politicising and empowering — as guiding principles — offer a pathway for just and inclusive biodiversity governance across scales, not only in relation to gender but also to diversity in its broader sense.**

Bridging gender equality, diversity, and biodiversity governance is not only a matter of fairness but a condition for resilient and lasting ecological transformation — one that values the knowledge, care, and leadership of those who sustain life in all its forms.

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Link to Sources

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Administrative Info About the Project

BIOTraCes (December 2022 to November 2026) is a [Horizon Europe](#) project that strives for an inclusive and nature-positive society. The key objective is to co-produce and develop knowledge and approaches that contribute to transformative changes for biodiversity and equity. 9 transformative biodiversity innovations spread across Europe will help to understand how a plurality of values and manifestations of power, lock-ins and leverage relates to behaviour (practices, actions, choices and decisions) and influences the underlying causes and indirect drivers of biodiversity decline.

BIOTraCes works together with [several sister projects](#) on Transformative Change.

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